

GENETIC VARIABILITY STUDIES FOR YIELD AND ITS CONTRIBUTING TRAITS IN *DESI* COTTON [*Gossypium arboreum* (L.)]

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Abstract

The variability studies revealed high estimates of phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) and genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for seed cotton yield per plant. High phenotypic coefficient of variation and moderate genotypic coefficient of variation was observed for the number of monopodia per plant. High heritability observed for the plant height, upper half mean length, fiber strength, uniformity ratio, the number of bolls per plant, micronaire and seed cotton yield per plant. The plant height, the number of bolls per plant and seed cotton yield per plant shows high heritability coupled with high genetic advance over mean indicating the preponderance of additive gene action in the inheritance of these traits. Genetic variability parameters were studied in thirty-two cotton genotypes raised during kharif 2023-2024 at Cotton Research Station, Mahboob Baugh Farm, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani in randomised block design with two replications. The high degree of variability was observed among all the genotypes for seed cotton yield and yield contributing traits. These genotypes could be utilized in the breeding programme for the improvement of desi cotton.

Key words- Desi cotton, variability, heritability, genetic advance

Introduction

Cotton is an important crop for sustainable economy of India and livelihood of the Indian Cotton Farming Community. Cotton was first cultivated as a fabric in the Indus River valley about 3000 B.C., now it is grown all over the world, mainly for its fibre. Often it is referred to as "White Gold" or King of fibre crop for its global importance and industrial utility (Romeu-Dalmau *et al.*, 2015). As it is the world's most important non-food agricultural commodity, cotton is essential for textile production, provides basic raw material to cotton textile industries, at present nearly 60 million people depend on cotton cultivation, marketing, processing, and export for their livelihood (Wendel *et al.*, 2012).

Among the 50 species of cotton, which are the world's most important crop for fiber, 44 are diploid ($2n=2x=26$) and remaining species are allotetraploids ($2n=4x=52$). There is total four cultivated species of cotton among these; diploid species (*G. arboreum* L. and *G. herbaceum* L.) are known as old world cotton and tetraploid (*G. hirsutum* L. and *G. barbadense* L.) as new world cotton which are grown commercially in India (Koebnick *et al.*, 2019). Cotton seed had gained the additional economic importance as a major contributor to edible oil, protein and other by-products (Hasan & Latha, 2017).

Genetic variability, combined with heritability, provides insights into the potential and scope for improvement in crop breeding programs. High heritability, when accompanied by substantial genetic advance, indicates the likely progress achievable through selection (Deguang *et al.*, 2018).

Material and Method

Thirty two genotypes of desi cotton were used for characterization, genetic variability in randomized block design with two replications during kharif 2023-2024. Plot size of *desi* cotton was 0.9×4.5 m² with spacing of 45 cm \times 22.5 cm. Recommended package of practices were followed as suitable for the climate conditions of Parbhani. Data was recorded on five randomly tagged plants for viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, number of monopodia, number of sympodia, plant height, number of bolls per plant, boll weight, ginning percentage, uniformity ratio, fiber strength, upper half mean length, micronaire and seed cotton yield per plant. Genetic variability parameters were assessed based on the formula given by Burton (1952). Heritability and genetic advance parameters were calculated according to Allard (1940) and Johnson *et al.* (1955).

Result And Discussion

The mean sum of squares due to treatments were found highly significant for all the characters studied (The values are presented in table number 1). Which reveals the presence of ample variability among the genotypes studied. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation, heritability, genetic advance and genetic advance as % of mean for various traits are presented in table number 2. The values of genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for days to 50 % flowering were recorded 1.99 and 2.32 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for plant height were recorded 19.17 and 19.42 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for number of monopodia were recorded 18.73 and 23.15 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for number of sympodia were recorded 15.90 and 18.99 per cent respectively.

The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for number of bolls per plant were recorded 18.47 and 20.01 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for boll weight were recorded 16.61 and 19.06 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for seed cotton yield per plant were recorded 18.90 and 21.54 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for ginning percentage were 4.86 and 7.28 per cent respectively.

The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for upper half mean length were recorded 6.50 and 6.75 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for fiber fineness were recorded 7.36 and 8.26 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for fiber strength were recorded 6.74 and 7.09 per cent respectively. The values for genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation for uniformity ratio were recorded 1.29 and 1.40 per cent respectively.

The highest estimate of phenotypic coefficient of variation and genotypic coefficient of variation was observed for seed cotton yield per plants (18.90 and 21.54 %). These findings are in agreement with the results reported by Jangid *et al.*, (2019) in american cotton. The moderate estimate of phenotypic coefficient and genotypic coefficient of variation was observed for number of sympodia (15.90 and 18.99 percent) followed by plant height (19.17 and 19.42 percent) and boll weight (16.61 and 19.06 per cent).

The moderate value for GCV and PCV was observed for number of bolls per plant and boll weight. Similar findings were also reported

Pinki *et al.*, (2018) in american cotton, Nawaz *et al.*, (2019) in american cotton, Bhatti *et al.*, (2020) in american cotton and Jangid *et al.*, (2019) in american cotton. The lowest PCV and GCV were observed for uniformity ratio (1.29 and 1.40 percent), fiber fineness (7.36 and 8.26 percent), upper half mean length (6.50 and 6.75 percent), days to 50 percent of flowering (1.99 and 2.32 percent), ginning percentage (4.86 and 7.28 percent). The lowest genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation were observed for fiber strength, fiber fineness, upper half mean length, days to 50% flowering, ginning percent and uniformity ratio. The similar results were reported by Chapepa *et al.*, (2020) in american cotton and Patankar (2021) in american cotton.

High heritability (73.46 %) coupled with low genetic advance (3.51) as per cent of mean were recorded for character days to 50 percent flowering. High heritability (65.42 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (31.20) as percent of mean were recorded for character number of monopodia per plant. High heritability (97.50 %) coupled with high genetic advance (39.00) as percent of mean were recorded for character plant height. High heritability (70.68 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (27.54) as percent of mean were recorded for character number of sympodia per plant. High heritability (85.23%) coupled with moderate genetic advance (35.13) as percent of mean were recorded for character number of bolls per plant. High heritability (75.93 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (29.81) as percent mean were recorded for boll weight. High heritability (76.95 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (34.15) as percent mean were recorded for seed cotton yield per plant.

Moderate heritability (44.57 %) coupled with low genetic advance (6.69) as a percent of mean were recorded for character ginning percent. High heritability (92.88 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (12.91) as percent of mean were recorded for character upper half mean length. High heritability (79.47 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (13.51) as percent of mean were recorded for character fiber fineness. High heritability (90.58 %) coupled with moderate genetic advance (13.22) as a percent of mean were recorded for character fiber strength. High heritability (85.62 %) coupled with low genetic advance (2.47) as a percent of mean were recorded for character uniformity ratio.

High value of heritability for all characters under study, were also reported by Sahar *et al.*, (2021) in american cotton for number of bolls per plant, seed cotton yield per plant, micronaire value and uniformity ratio. Jangid *et al.*, (2019) recorded heritability estimates in american cotton for seed cotton yield, fiber length, fiber strength, plant height, number of bolls per plant. Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) recorded heritability estimates in desi cotton for fiber strength, upper half mean length, boll weight, ginning percent, boll number per plant and Nikhil *et al.*, (2023) in american cotton for number of sympodia per plant and number of boll per plant.

Genetic advance as percent of mean ranged from 2.47 to 39.00. Seed cotton yield per plant, number of bolls per plant, number of monopodia and plant height recorded high genetic advance as a percent of mean, while number of sympodia per plant, fiber strength, upper half mean length, fiber fineness and boll weight recorded moderate genetic advance as a percent of mean. In this study, the low value of genetic advance as a percentage of mean was found for days to 50% flowering, ginning percentage and uniformity ratio.

These results are in conformity with the studies Jangid *et al.* (2019) in american cotton recorded high genetic advance as per cent of mean for seed cotton yield per plant, lint index and number of bolls per plant, Valu *et al.*, (2021) in desi cotton for number of bolls per plants, Kumar *et al.*, (2024) in desi cotton for seed cotton yield per plant, plant height and number of bolls per plant, Nandhini *et al.*, (2019) in american cotton for fiber fineness/micronaire value and uniformity ratio.

It was suggested that when calculating genetic progress during selection, it is important to evaluate both heritability and genetic advance as a percent mean of the traits rather than considering each character individually. The heritability associated with genetic advance as per cent of mean is more useful for predicting seed cotton yield under phenotypic selection than heritability estimations alone. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as per cent mean suggests that most likely the heritability is due to additive gene action and selection may be successful. The traits seed cotton yield per plant, number of bolls per plant and plant height indicate high estimates of heritability accompanied with high genetic advance as per cent of mean indicating additive gene action and thus selection for these characters in genetically diverse material would be effective for desired genetic improvement. Similar results were reported by Gnanasakeran *et al.*, (2020) in american cotton for number of bolls per plant and seed cotton yield per plant, Jogender *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton for plant height, number of bolls per plant and seed cotton yield per plant and Sangwan *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton for seed cotton yield per plant. The high heritability with moderate genetic advance as a per cent of mean indicating the presence of nonadditive gene action. The characters, number of sympodia per plant, fiber strength, upper half mean length, fiber fineness and boll weight showed high heritability with moderate genetic advance. Similar results were reported by Jogender *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton for uniformity ratio and Fatima *et al.*, (2021) in desi cotton for fiber strength. The high heritability with low genetic advance as per cent of mean indicates the presence of non-additive gene action. The traits, days to 50 percent flowering, ginning percentage and uniformity ratio shows high heritability accompanied with low genetic advance as per cent mean. Similar result was reported by Sagar *et al.*, (2023) in desi cotton.

Table 1: Analysis of variance for morphological, yield contributing and fibre characters in cotton

Sr. no.	Characters	Mean sum of squares		
		Replication (1)	Treatment (49)	Error (49)
1	Days to 50% flowering	1.26	4.05**	0.62
2	No. of monopodia	1.00	4.57**	0.95
3	No. of sympodia	0.52	5.77**	0.99
4	Plant height (cm)	26.46	509.75**	6.43
5	No. of bolls (gm)	2.48	18.18**	1.45
6	Boll weight (gm)	0.02	0.69**	0.09
7	Ginning %	9.25	9.40**	3.60
8	Uniformity ratio	0.72	2.40**	0.19
9	Fibre strength (g tex ⁻¹)	0.05	6.73**	0.33
10	UHML (mm)	0.00068	6.30**	0.23
11	Micronaire (µg/in)	0.00016	0.40**	0.05
12	Seed cotton yield/plant	0.45	92.63**	12.06

*, **significant at 5 and 1 percent level, respectively.

Table 2: Parameter of genetic variability for morphological, yield contributing and fibre characters in cotton

Characters	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	Heritability (BS) (%)	Genetic advance (GA)	Genetic advance as % of Mean (GAM)	Genotypic Variance (GV)	Phenotypic Variance (PV)
Days to 50 % flowering	1.99	2.32	73.46	2.31	3.51	1.71	2.33
Number of monopodia	18.73	23.15	65.42	2.24	31.20	1.81	2.76
Number of sympodia	15.90	18.99	70.68	2.68	27.54	2.39	3.38
Plant height (cm)	19.17	19.42	97.50	32.27	39.00	251.66	258.10
Number of bolls/plant	18.47	20.01	85.23	5.50	35.13	8.36	9.81
Boll Weight (gm)	16.61	19.06	75.93	0.98	29.81	0.30	0.40
Ginning percentage (%)	4.86	7.28	44.58	2.34	6.69	2.89	6.50
Uniformity Ratio (%)	1.29	1.40	85.62	2.01	2.47	1.11	1.30
Fiber Strength (g/tex)	6.74	7.09	90.58	3.50	13.22	3.20	3.53
Upper half mean length(mm)	6.50	6.75	92.88	3.46	12.91	3.03	3.27
Micronaire (µg/inch)	7.36	8.26	79.47	0.78	13.51	0.18	0.22
Seed cotton yield per plant (gm)	18.90	21.54	76.95	11.47	34.15	40.28	52.35

GV-Genotypic variance, PCV-Phenotypic co-efficient of variation (%), GCV-Genotypic co-efficient of variation (%), PV-Phenotypic Variance, BS-Heritability(%), GAM-Genetic Advance as % mean, GA-Genetic Advance

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* Original not seen.